

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVE ELECTROMECHANICAL COUPLING OF A VIBRATING AIRCRAFT-TYPE HYBRID HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL WITH BONDED PIEZOELECTRIC d_{31} MACRO-FIBRE COMPOSITE (MFC) PATCH

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Abstract. This work presents the *experimental evaluation* challenges of the modal effective *Electro-Mechanical Coupling Coefficient* (EMCC) of a *hybrid sandwich plate*, made of regular (hexagonal) Aluminium *honeycomb core* and woven glass fibre-reinforced polymer *composite faces*, on which is bonded a piezoelectric transverse response (d_{31}) *Macro-Fibre Composite* (MFC) large patch. The testing challenges come from the very *light weight* of the hybrid sandwich panel and the resulting difficulties to consider, without damaging it, different mechanical boundary conditions (BCs) along its lateral edges. This experimental campaign, using an *impedance analyser*, complements an earlier one that used an LCR meter. The latter provided only the EMCC of the first three electro-mechanically coupled modes under free-free (F-F) BCs, while the former reached *more accurately* eight ones for F-F and *clamped-free* (cantilever) BCs. Beside graphical form, the obtained frequency and effective EMCC results are given in tabular form, so that they can be used as reference for validating/correlating future numerical models.

Keywords: Experiment; EMCC; Vibration; Hybrid honeycomb sandwich; Piezoelectric; MFC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hybrid honeycomb sandwiches, made of different materials for the core and faces, find popular usage as trim panels in modern aircraft structures for alleviating their weight, noise or vibration. Hybridization can be reached by combining Aluminium (Al) [1-3], paper [1, 4, 5] and Carbon (CFRP) [2, 4, 5] or Glass (GFRP) [3, 6, 7] Fibre-Reinforced Polymer woven *composite materials*. Hybrid honeycomb sandwiches are often functionalized through bonding *piezoelectric* (PE) ceramic [1, 2] or *Macro-Fibre Composite* (MFC) [4-7] patches that are used as sensors and actuators for wave propagation [1, 2], structural health monitoring [5] and active vibration control [4]. Besides, for vibration-based transduction applications, like PE shunted damping (PSD) and energy harvesting (PEH), the so-called modal effective *Electro-Mechanical Coupling Coefficient* (EMCC) is a key performance indicator [8] that can be maximized by adequately selecting the host-patch materials couple and optimally positioning the patch on the host laminated CFRP composite or hybrid (GFRP skins, Al core) honeycomb sandwich structures [6]. However, except the earlier works [6, 7], no others have been found in the open literature on the experimental evaluation of the modal effective EMCC of hybrid honeycomb sandwiches bonded with MFC patches. Therefore, this work presents for the first time *Experimental Impedance Analyser (EIA)*-based evaluation challenges of the modal effective EMCC of a *hybrid sandwich plate*, made of regular (hexagonal) *Al honeycomb core* and woven *GFRP composite faces*, on which is bonded a PE *transverse mode* (d_{31}) MFC large patch. The testing challenges come from the very *light weight* of the panel and the resulting difficulties to consider, without damaging it, *different mechanical Boundary Conditions* (BCs), like free-free (F-F) and clamped-free (C-F) lateral edges of the hybrid sandwich [3]. This new campaign complements an LCR (Inductance-L, Capacitance-C, Resistance-R) meter-based earlier one [6, 7], that provided only the EMCC of the first three *electromechanically coupled modes* (EMC), by reaching *more accurately* eight ones under F-F and C-F (*cantilever*) BCs.

In the following, first, the next section describes the experimental setup, materials and devices. Then, the third section presents the resulting experimental modal analyses (EMA) of the EIA measurements and their use for the *Short-Circuit* (SC) and *Open-Circuit* (OC) frequencies extractions and modal effective EMCC post-treatments. Next, the EIA measurements and results are compared to those of experimental LCR meter analyses for the respectively considered F-F or/and C-F BCs. The latter are popular in PSD and PEH, while the former are useful for inverse identification. Finally, conclusions and perspectives are given as a closure.

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2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP: MATERIALS AND DEVICES

This section describes the EMA setup, its measurement devices and the aircraft-type hybrid honeycomb sandwich and surface-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch materials used for the experimental evaluation of the modal effective EMCC of such vibrating smart structure under F-F (Figure 1a) and C-F (Figure 1b) BCs at its lateral edges. For this, the *impedance analyzer* WK 6500B from Wayne Kerr (WK), shown in Figure 1, is used to graphically display the *module* and *phase* of the *voltage-to-current ratio* of the *capacitance* of the d_{31} MFC patch, that is surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under the considered two BCs. The *excitation voltage* was fixed to 1V, while the *impedance analyzer resolution* was set to 1600 points for a considered frequency range.

Figure 1: EIA setup for modal effective EMCC evaluation under (a) F-F and (b) C-F BCs.

As shown in Figure 1a and zoomed-in in Figure 2a, the F-F BCs were realized by posing the tested smart structure on two foam pieces, while the C-F BCs were realized by accurately (with good quality alignment) fastening one lateral edge along 1 cm, as shown in Figure 1b and zoomed-in in Figure 2b. It is worthy to mention that the influence of the smart coupon position on the foams was found negligible, as considering two different positions led to the same *resonant* (SC) and *anti-resonant* (OC) frequencies of their related MFC *capacitances*.

Figure 2: Zoom-in of Figure 1 on realized (a) F-F BCs and (b) C-F BCs' clamp.

The optimal positioning of the MFC patch on the vibrating hybrid sandwich honeycomb is modal shape and BCs-dependent [9]. Hence, a numerical modal analysis (NMA) of the bare honeycomb sandwich coupon was conducted, using a developed *detailed* finite element (FE) approach [3], in order to locate the maxima of the *modal strain energy* (MSE) where to bond the MFC patch. The resulting optimized configuration is that in Figure 2a, where the MFC patch is located 3 cm from one lateral edge (see also Figure 1b) and *centered* along the host *width*. This *optimal* position *maximizes* the effective EMCC of the *first mode*, the target of the PSD and PEH applications.

The PE d_{31} MFC patch (M-8528-P2), from Smart Materials GmbH (Germany), has global in-plane dimensions of $103 \times 31 \text{ mm}^2$ and useful *active area* ones of $85 \times 28 \text{ mm}^2$ while its *thickness* is 0.3 mm. In order to connect it to the impedance analyzer (Figure 1), very thin wires were soldered to its net-like electrodes' dedicated soldering pads (see Figure 2a). The MFC patch was *glued* with *Cyanolit* (super glue) to one of the GFRP skins of the hybrid honeycomb sandwich, which has length x width x thickness of $183 \times 52 \times 4.6 \text{ mm}^3$. More details on the latter host structure geometrical and material properties can be found in [3]. The combined hybrid honeycomb sandwich and MFC patch have a measured mass of 13.75 g, indicating a *very light* smart structure. Considering the protecting polyamide film, electrodes, soldering pads and glue allowed to *update* the d_{31} MFC patch volume mass density to 6300 Kg/m^3 (*active area*-based value is 5440 Kg/m^3 [10]).

3 EXPERIMENTAL IMPEDANCE ANALYSES: FREQUENCIES & EFFECTIVE EMCC

This section first presents the graphical displays of the *absolute* and *phase* of the *voltage-to-current ratio* of the *capacitance* of the d_{31} MFC patch that is surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under the considered two BCs (F-F and C-F). Then, the extracted SC and OC frequencies, approximating respectively the *resonant* (r) and *anti-resonant* (a) ones, are tabulated with the post-treated *experimental* (e) EMCC (K_e^2) from [11]:

$$K_e^2 (\%) = 100 \frac{f_a^2 - f_r^2}{f_a^2} \quad (1)$$

A slightly different, called *numerical* (n), EMCC expression is traditionally used in PSD applications:

$$K_n^2 (\%) = 100 \frac{f_{oc}^2 - f_{sc}^2}{f_{sc}^2} \quad (2)$$

However, above EMCC expressions were shown [11] to be related by this one:

$$K_e^2 \approx \frac{K_n^2}{K_n^2 + 1} \quad (3)$$

Nevertheless, when $K_n^2 \ll 1$, $K_e^2 \approx K_n^2$ and either of the expressions can be used for evaluating the EMCC.

3.1 Free-free configuration

The module and phase of the capacitance of the F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch are shown in Figure 3, first, for a large (300 Hz-11 kHz) frequency range, in order to evaluate the number of modes present in this range. Then, zooms illustrate missing modes (Figure 4a) or for accurate identification (Figure 4b).

Figure 3: Capacitance module and phase spectra of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Figure 4: Capacitance module and phase spectra of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

As in Figure 5, the phase peak corresponds to the inflexion point between resonance and anti-resonance peaks.

Figure 5: Capacitance combined module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Next, a zoom-in on each mode is displayed in order to identify its resonant (SC) and anti-resonant (OC) frequencies that correspond, respectively, to the maximum and minimum of the capacitance module or the points of inflexion of the ascending and descending branches of the phase, as illustrated in Figure 6 for the first mode.

Figure 6: Identification of mode 1 (a) resonant (SC) and anti-resonant (OC) frequencies from module and phase.

The earlier procedure is applied for identifying the *eight modes*, numbered in Figure 3 and Figure 4, leading to the frequencies and effective EMCC summarized in Table 1. The latter confirms that the *highest* effective EMCC is obtained for the *first mode*, target of PSD and PEH applications. Besides, following (1) and (2) and as $f_{a,OC} > f_{r,SC}$, $K_n^2 > K_e^2$; hence, the numerical EMCC *overestimates* the experimental one. Nevertheless, the differences between them reduces as the former is approaching unity. Besides, it is worthy to recall that the impedance analyzer provides only the characteristics of the EMC modes. Hence, as the *in-plane* (x-y) *bending* and *torsion* modes are known to be electro-mechanically *uncoupled* [9, 11], the modes in Table 1 are the *transverse* (x-z) *bending* modes only. This recall is to be taken into account when using these experimental tabulated results as a reference for validating/correlating numerical (FE for example) ones. Specifically, the order of modes shown in the first column of Table 1 should be made consistent with that resulting from the numerical analysis. That is, the consistent modes order is correctly obtained only after modal shapes (deformation) visualizations.

Table 1: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_r, f_{SC}	f_a, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	600.00	618.07	5.76	6.11
2	1502.92	1523.39	2.67	2.74
3	2751.82	2788.52	2.61	2.69
4	4184.76	4242.32	2.70	2.77
5	6981.76	7089.31	3.01	3.10
6	7722.69	7850.82	3.24	3.35
7	7988.71	8061.02	1.79	1.82
8	8170.71	8319.28	3.54	3.67

3.2 Clamped-free configuration

Under the *same measurement conditions* as the F-F configuration, the module and phase of the capacitance of the C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch are shown in Figure 7, first, for the a wide (global) frequency range (100 Hz-8 kHz) in order to evaluate the number of modes present in this range. It can be seen that the latter shows *six modes* that have much lower frequencies than those in Figure 3, due to the clamp presence.

Figure 7: Capacitance module and phase spectra of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Then, the same zoom-in procedure is applied for accurately identifying the *six modes*, numbered in Figure 7, leading to the frequencies and effective EMCC shown in Table 2 from which similar remarks as from Table 1 can be retained, except that the *highest* EMCC (lower value) is here obtained for the *fourth mode* despite its low peak.

Table 2: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_i, f_{SC}	f_a, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	107.25	108.76	2.84	2.76
2	515.46	523.06	2.97	2.88
3	1368.38	1381.45	1.92	1.88
4	2713.41	2769.09	4.15	3.98
5	3194.49	3255.56	3.86	3.72
6	3582.33	3646.46	3.61	3.49

4 COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL LCR METER ANALYSES

This section aims to compare the *LCM Meter*-based measured (*mode-by-mode* and *frequency-by-frequency*) *impedance* (module and phase) figures, tabulated extracted frequencies and post-treated effective EMCC of the PE d_{31} MFC patch, surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under F-F BCs that were *realized differently*, as this first experimental campaign was conducted few years earlier than the present one. Indeed, the F-F BCs were here realized by *wire suspension* of the smart hybrid honeycomb sandwich, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: *Wire suspension*-realized F-F BCs of the smart hybrid honeycomb sandwich.

The impedance module and phase, measured by an LCR meter, are shown graphically in Figure 9 for the first EMC mode and Figure 10 for the second one. From the latter, notice the poor accuracy around the curves' peaks, due to the LCM meter low frequency resolution (large steps), that shall affect the accuracy of the extraction of the impedance *minimum* (*anti-resonant*, SC) and *maximum* (*resonant*, OC) frequencies (oppositely to the capacitance characteristics) and the EMCC post-treated from them. The corresponding results are shown in Table 3.

Figure 9: EMC mode 1 impedance module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Figure 10: EMC mode 2 impedance module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Table 3: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_a, f_{SC}	f_r, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	590.55	600	3.13	3.23
2	1495	1525	3.90	4.05

Despite the inaccuracy of extractions, the $a_{,SC}$ and $r_{,OC}$ frequencies given in Table 3 show small *relative deviations* (with those in Table 1 that are taken as *reference*, due to their extractions accuracy), particularly for EMC mode 2, of, respectively, -1.57% and -2.92% for EMC mode 1, and -0.53% and 0.11% for EMC mode 2. However, the relative deviations of the EMCC are much higher ($\sim \pm 47\%$, with ‘-’ for mode 1 and ‘+’ for mode 2) as they are proportional to the *frequency measurement resolution* and the *inverse of EMCC values* [12].

5 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Impedance analyser-based experimental evaluations of the modal effective EMCC of a vibrating *hybrid Al honeycomb-woven GFRP composite faces sandwich plate*, bonded with a PE d_{31} MFC large patch, were presented in figures and tables for F-F and C-F lateral edges of the smart panel. The extracted frequencies and post-treated effective EMCC were compared to those from earlier LCR meter-based experimental evaluations [6, 7]. The latter provided only the EMCC of the first two EMC modes under F-F BCs, while the former reached *more accurately eight modes* for F-F and C-F BCs. The present experimental campaign confirmed that the *highest* effective EMCC is that of the *fundamental mode*, the target of PSD and PEH applications, while the earlier experimental campaign showed *lower* graphical and peak (resonant/anti-resonant) frequency extraction *accuracy*, due to the low frequency resolution of the LCR meter. Nevertheless, the provided *tabulated results* of both experimental campaigns can be of valuable use as *reference* for validating/correlating future numerical models. In particular, the use of the detailed FE approach [3] gives a good perspective of the present work, as this will allow the *experimental validation* of the recently *FE-homogenized* 3D electromechanical properties of the here described PE d_{31} MFC [13].

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